

IMPACT OF DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION ON ORGANIZATIONAL PERFORMANCE IN RETAIL INDUSTRY IN CAPETOWN, SOUTH AFRICA

Stallone Msamba (MBA, PGDip, fCMgr)

Independent Researcher

msambastallone@yahoo.com

Abstract

Digital transformation is the integration of digital technology and business strategies in all aspects of business or organization to change how the business operates and deliver value to stakeholders. Digital transformation improves organization performance efficiency, customer experience, and gains competitive advantage in the market. The research investigates the impact of digital transformation on organization performance in retail industry in Cape Town, South Africa. The research investigates key drivers such as operation efficiency, technology advancement, cybersecurity, omnichannel retailing, customer behavior, and data-driven decision-making, enabling the adoption of digital transformation in the retail industry. The research investigates how digital transformation initiatives such omnichannel, data analytics, e-commerce, Customer Relationship Management systems, artificial intelligence improves operation efficiency, customer experience and gain competitive advantage. The research investigates the impact of digital transformation on financial performance metrics, such as revenue and cost efficiency. The research also investigates how digital transformation influence operation efficiency through collaboration, automation, data-driven decision-making, and supply chain management. The research investigates the gap between the research background and current research to determine future research on digital transformation in the retail industry. The p investigates challenges and barriers such as skill gap, digital literacy, poor infrastructure, employee resistance, cost constraints, limited access, and regulatory compliance, and how it is affecting the adoption of digital transformation in the retail industry in South Africa.

Keywords

Digital transformation

Retail Industry

Operation efficiency

Omnichannel

Competitive advantage

Table of Contents.....	1
Abstract.....	i
1.0 Introduction.....	1
2.0 Research Aims.....	3
3.0 Research objectives.....	4
4.0 Research background.....	4
4.1 Sources of background research.....	5
4.1.1 <i>Industry trends</i>	5
4.1.2 <i>End-user trends</i>	6
4.2 Identifying the gap in background research.....	7
5.0 Comparing and Contrasting different perspectives in research.....	8
6.0 Identifying connections between research and current knowledge.....	9
7.0 Research approach.....	9
8.0 Data analysis.....	10
9.0 Interpretation of findings.....	11
10.0 Limitations of the findings.....	11
11.0 Barriers of digital transformation facing retail industry.....	12
12.0 References.....	13

1.0 Introduction

Digital transformation refers to the incorporation into all aspects of business such as products, processes, and strategies to change how the business organization operates and deliver value to customers. Digital transformation has influence on traditional enterprises, facilitating the provision of their existing production, operational and managerial processes (Vial, 2019). Digital transformation is driven by tangible shifts in the role of technology within the organization (Tang, 2021). Digital transformation includes emerging technologies such as artificial intelligence, big-data analytics, cloud computing, and AI supply chain management. Digital transformation increases sales, sustainability, and improves customer satisfaction, operational efficiency, and competitive advantage.

Digital transformation creates new or modify existing business models and processes to support the transformation of the organization's structure, relationship, and resources (*Brynjolfsson and Hitt, 2000*). The adoption of digital transformation is not a choice but a response to the constant change of the modern marketplace. Digital transformation in the retail industry involves adoption of omnichannel strategies to improve customer experience and gain competitive advantage which significantly drives customer loyalty and retention (*Trenz et al, 2021*). The adoption of E-commerce such as Virtual Reality and Augmented Reality improves customer experience, gains competitive advantage and loyalty. Adopting and implementing AI-inventory management systems which improve customer operational experience and gain competitive advantage. Implementing data analytic tools improves customer experience through Customer Relationship Management (CRM) system

Digital transformation changes how the business operates by changing the processes, workflows, culture, and communication. Digital transformation affects operations by bringing together data across all areas of the business. Personalization of customers through Customer Relationship Management (CRM) systems enables retailers to offer the most suitable products at the right time and in the best place to please customers (*Sunikka and Bregge, 2012*). Omnichannel retailing enables retailers to use multiple sources of different channels such as the internet, mobile apps, and social media to connect with customers (*Shi et al, 2020*). Digital transformation has improved operation efficiency through AI-inventory management systems which use real-time data analytics to manage stock levels, mitigate stockouts, and forecasts. Digital transformation improves competitive advantages. Competitive advantage is tied to an organization's ability to embrace modern technologies swiftly and effectively (*Faraj and Leonardi, 2022*). Retailers who have adopted and implement digital transformation have better chance of getting competitive edge in the market than those who are using traditional marketing tools because digital transformation tools such as CRM improves customer engagement, retention, and loyalty. Digital transformation improves adaptability and innovations because technology is always evolving which means all activities and processes also changes such as consumer preference, modern technologies, and digital transformation enables retailers to prepare for the future innovations and disruptions to cope with the changes and expectations from customers and market.

2.0 Research Aims

The main aim of the research is to implement digital transformation tools such as omnichannel strategies, data analytics, CRM systems to improve customer satisfaction, loyalty to drive business growth, and revenues. The project aims at developing and implementing omnichannel

strategies by combining various channels including mobile apps, websites, and in-store to improve customer experience. Implementing AI-inventory management systems which use artificial intelligence and data to improve operation efficiency to reduce costs. The project aims to upgrade the Customer Relationship Management systems which analyses customer data to make targeted marketing which customer experience improves engagement. The project aims to implement data analytics which analyzes consumer behavior, improve data-driven decision-making, and inventory management.

3.0 Research objectives

The transformation research objectives are to investigate the impact of digital transformation strategies to improve customer experience, operation efficiency, revenue growth, and gain competition in the market. Omnichannel strategies, data analytics, e-commerce and customer relationship management systems improve customer experience. Data analytics improve operation efficiency, revenue growth, gain competitive edge, and customer experience. Personalization improves customer experience.

Developing and integrating both online and offline channels to improve shopping experience. Omnichannel system enhances shopping experience as customers shop across in-store, mobile apps and websites and provides seamless shopping experience and convenience as customers can shop anytime and anywhere accessing a wide range of products (*Pantano and Viassone, 2015*). Enhancing the role of data analytics by implementing advanced data analytic tools to improve decision making, enhance operation efficiency, and inventory management. Data analytics enables retailers to make data-driven from customer historical purchases and preferences, and this improves engagement and customer loyalty and retention. Adopting and implementing AI-inventory management systems improves operation efficiency as they manage stock levels preventing overstock and provide forecasting of demand as data analytic tools provide quality data-driven decision making. Personalization of customers improves communication, collaboration, increases sales and engagement between customers and retailers, which improves customer loyalty and retention. The Customer Relationship Management system creates innovative approaches to understanding, pinpointing, and satisfying customer needs (*Rathole, 2019*). Enhancing E-commerce technologies such Augmented Reality and Virtual Reality improves shopping experience, and this improves customer retention and conversion rates because the technology enables customers to shop online or in-store for virtual try-ons. Implementing digital transformation tools improves operation efficiency through automation processes and improves inventory

management as it uses data analytic tools to manage stock level, reduce costs, and forecast demand.

4.0 Research background

Digital transformation in modern times is highly recognized as a key driver to improve economic competitiveness and enhance organizational efficiency in emerging economies. In South Africa, the adoption of digital technologies across different sectors of organization has increased over the past decade, supported by national efforts to modernize public and private institutions. The retail industry is rapidly undergoing digital transformation adoption, which is driven by changing consumer behavior and technological innovations. In the Western Cape, e-commerce platforms such as Takealot have scaled significantly, while traditional stores including Pick n Pay, ShopRite, Spur and Woolworths are adopting digital transformation by integrating digital services like online shopping and digital payments to stay competitive. The main key drivers which have enabled organizations to adopt digital transformation include demand for increased customer experience, operation efficiency, supply chain management, and inventory management. Despite organizations adopting digital transformation, the rate of adoption is uneven between large retailers and small retailers due to lack of resources to invest in digital tools, e-commerce platforms, and advanced digital infrastructure. Large retailers can invest while small retailers face challenges in digital skills, financial constraints, and adapting legacy systems. Research from different researchers suggest digital transformation can significantly improve organizational performance through increased sales, improved operational efficiency, better customer engagement while enabling organization gain competitive advantage. Despite organizations adopting digital transformation and doing well, the research focusing on problems that affect digital transformation adoption remains relatively scarce, and this research aims to highlight the gap that exists.

4.1 Sources of background research

This chapter focused on a well-rounded analysis of current sources of the digital transformation project in retail industry in Cape Town, South Africa. The main purpose of analyzing the background research of current sources of digital transformation is to establish a strong project foundation by drawing insights from existing research and industry developments. The project

obtained study materials from leader blogs, journals, industry reports and academic experts. The strong background research supports the project rationale while identifying the gaps that exist between past research and current research to determine the future. The strong background research supports the project rationale while identifying the gaps that exist between past research and current research to determine the future.

4.1.1 Industry trends

Retail industry trends are changes, developments and patterns influenced by consumer behavior, technology advancement, market, and regulatory changes.

Omnichannel retailing. Retailers are adopting omnichannel strategies which involve combining complex technology such as in-store systems, online stores, mobile apps, and information technology structure (Cao and Li, 2018). Omnichannel removes barriers between each channel to provide seamless, organically connected consumer experience (Zhang et al, 2024).

Sustainability and ethical retailing. Retailers are adopting sustainability practices because of increased awareness from customers which is fueled by information from social media emphasizing customers to consider ethical implications of their purchases. Corporate social responsibility is an essential criterion for organizations to build brands and reputations that make a difference, maintain trust with customers, and improve public image (Vuong et al, 2024).

Personalization. Retailers are implementing AI-personalization tools by using large amount of data related to consumer shopping behavior, consumer buying habits web browsing and consumer preferences to make data-driven decisions to improve customer experience (Shukla and Gupta, 2022). Personalized marketing is important in the retail industry because it improves customer loyalty and retention. Artificial intelligence has transformed consumer demands and expectations as many customers want recommendations that reflect their past purchases and references (Reigger et al, 2021).

Enhanced payment systems. Retailers are adopting advanced payment systems to gain a competitive advantage in a highly competitive business environment. Businesses that have implemented payment strategies have an edge in competition in the market because they offer efficiency, speed, and reliable transactions. Digital payment systems include mobile wallets,

contactless payments, and online payments which improve streamline operations and customer satisfaction (*Brown et al, 2024*).

Artificial intelligence. Artificial intelligence is at the center of transformation which helps organizations improve operations efficiency and decision making in the retail industry also improving performance, and engagement with customers (*Krishnan et al, 2022*). AI-data driven provides accurate forecasting and prediction of customer while AI-inventory management improves the management of stock levels, reduces costs, and automation improves customer services such as chatbots.

4.1.2 End-user trends

The end-user trends in South Africa retail industry are always evolving and is influenced by technological changes, changing society lifestyle and economic conditions faced by consumers.

Increased online shopping. Increased mobile devices have increased customers accessing online retail platforms to compare prices, browse various products, and make purchases. This has made retailers focus on online shopping strategies and the increase in online shopping has made shopping very convenient as customers can shop online at any given time without wasting time going to the shops. Online shopping increases online retail sales and reduces costs and plays an important role in determining how effective online retailers can leverage innovative technology to deliver customer satisfaction (*Gupta et al, 2020*).

Demand for omnichannel shopping. With advanced digital technology, consumers in retail expect both online and offline channels to offer seamless and flexible shopping experience (*Cotarelo et al, 2021*). The omnichannel channel shopping experience offers consistency in terms of prices whether online or offline it offers the same price and promotions offered on online is offered offline and this has enabled retailers to prioritize customers to access both online and offline shopping experience.

Price sensitivity. Price plays a big role when customers are evaluating product options and making purchase options (*Hsu et al, 2017*). Price influences customer judgement about brand pricing relative to competitors for consumers to make decisions (*Niedrich et al, 2009*). Consumers tend to explore deals, discounts, and promotions on both offline and online

channels to choose the best one. Consumers also buy in bulk to save money. Retailers are forced to adopt digital transformation so that they can meet the needs set by consumers.

Health and wellness consciousness. There is an increase in calls from health-conscious customers who want retailers to meet their evolving needs and products such as food, beverages, and beauty categories. Most customers are looking for products which are environmentally friendly, such as organic natural products and locally sourced products. Consumers are constantly evaluating products, conducting research, and re-evaluating the ways stores, products and brands meet their needs (Anthony, 2024).

Demand for personalized experience. Consumers expect personalized shopping experience across digital platforms attached to their purchase history and preference. Implementing personalization strategies can improve customer communication and customer engagement (Jain et al, 2021). Artificial intelligence driven personalization platforms such as Customer Relationship Management are used to engage customers. Loyalty programs are increasingly personalized as they offer reward deals and discounts because consumers want to maximize their spending value.

4.2 Identifying the gap in background research

There exists a significant research gap regarding how digital transformation initiatives—such as omnichannel integration, customer relationship management (CRM) systems, and data analytics are implemented and optimized within the retail industry in Cape Town, South Africa. While extensive research and reports by global institutions such as McKinsey, Deloitte, and Gartner provide information⁶ into digital transformation trends in developed economies, there is limited empirical evidence addressing the unique challenges and opportunities within the South African context. Factors such as inadequate digital infrastructure, economic constraints, limited internet access, and varying consumer preferences influence the adoption and effectiveness of digital tools locally. Moreover, there is an insufficient understanding of how local retailers align these technologies with customer experience and operational efficiency. This lack of localized research creates a critical gap in knowledge and calls for further investigation into context-specific digital transformation strategies that can drive sustainable business performance.

5.0 Comparing and Contrasting different perspectives in research

Comparing different perspectives involves highlighting similarities, differences, and gaps from different viewpoints on key topics such as customer-centric solutions, artificial intelligence, and digital transformation.

McKinsey report on omnichannel integration focuses on customers centric experience and explained that the integration of online and offline channels increases sales, customer retention and loyalty while Gartner focuses on the technology and explain that infrastructure such as cloud platforms, AI-driven analytics and automated inventory systems is the backbone of omnichannel strategies. Both reports focus on the achievement of the strategy and thus the goal of the project.

PwC report on AI-inventory management systems focuses on how the system improves organization efficiency by managing stock levels, reducing costs by forecasting the demand from sales data while the Harvard business review focuses on how the system should not only focus on operation efficiency but also products that are on high demand both online and offline. Both perspectives focus on the management of inventory through artificial intelligence to improve efficiency.

MIS Quarterly report on personalization and Customer Relationship Management (CRM) Systems focuses on the importance of data-driven personalization where CRM uses past purchases, preferences and browse history to create personalized shopping experience while the journal of retailing focuses on how CRM can be used to create customer segment groups so that it can focus on those groups which have common preferences using behavior data and this allows targeted marketing campaigns. Both perspectives focus on the personalization of customers to make data-driven decisions.

6.0 Identifying connections between research and current knowledge

The connection between the research and current knowledge is crucial to the Transformation Project Definition because it extends the understanding of the project by linking the existing studies and reports and how they align with technology advancement, trends, and consumer behavior.

The McKinsey report of 2024 on retail detailed how omnichannel strategies improve customer loyalty, retention and satisfaction through personalized marketing and its success depends on integration of online and offline channels. The current knowledge of omnichannel strategies is that consumers expect seamless transition between websites, mobile apps, and physical stores, and this is at a global level. At the local level, omnichannel strategies are slow in terms of adoption due to poor infrastructure and digital literacy differences. The connection between them is that omnichannel improves sales and customer experience. However, the current knowledge is affected by infrastructure, and this can be improved by integrating in-store data and mobile apps.

The PwC report of 2023 on inventory management systems detailed how AI improves stock accuracy, reduces costs, and manages the level of stock but forecasting demand. The current knowledge of the system is that many retailers globally are adopting the strategy. Locally, the strategy of adoption is slow due to limited access to AI tools and inconsistent supply chains, even though many retailers recognize the importance of the AI-inventory management systems. The connection between the research and current knowledge is that the research report highlights the importance of the system to reduce costs and improve management of stock level. This aligns with current knowledge, and the adoption of the system can overcome supply chain disruptions in Cape Town.

7.0 Research approach

The researcher adopted the secondary qualitative research methodology because the approach explores rich insight information about complex, technical, and strategic aspects of the organization. A qualitative approach was chosen because it focuses on developing an understanding of an experience through exploration and interpretation from different researchers. The approach enables the use of pre-existing data with the aim of providing an additional or different understanding of the problem (*Largan and Morris, 2019*). The explanatory nature of the digital transformation process enabled the adoption of the approach as it allows in-depth understanding of rich, detailed insight such as complexity of consumer behavior, market trends and patterns and stakeholder perspectives. A qualitative approach also offers flexibility to adapt to new emerging data collection and analysis and allows adjustment during data collection. The qualitative approach enables theory development because it links past theories and present theories to formulate future theories. A qualitative data approach is cost effective as it requires small sample, flexible designs which adapt to time constraints. The qualitative approach enables discovering the latest information and when information is not

well understood. The qualitative methodology enabled robust explanations of the reviewed data because it allowed the researcher to identify exact moments, patterns, and themes which led to specific behavior being carried out (*Miles and Huberman, 1994*).

8.0 Interpretation of findings

Customer experience. Customer experience is one of the key drivers for the adoption of digital transformation in the retail industry. Personalization, CRM, and omnichannel integration play a key role in improving customer experience, loyalty, and engagement. E-commerce such as AR and VR improve customer experience, loyalty, and retention. Through data-driven personalization, retailers can better understand customer preferences, leading to improved engagement and long-term brand relationships.

Operational efficiency. Artificial intelligence and automation improve operation through data analytics, which is critical for inventory management and decision-making. AI-powered analytics provide real-time insights for effective inventory management, reducing waste, and improving supply chain accuracy. Automated systems streamline processes, minimize human error, and enable faster response to market demands.

Innovation capabilities. Big data analytics through AI-inventory management systems improve decision-making by forecasting trends and demand enhancing competitive advantage in the market. This predictive capacity allows firms to respond proactively to changing consumer behavior, strengthening their competitiveness and innovation culture within the retail ecosystem.

Challenges and solutions. The resistance of employees to adopt digital technology is a big concern and needs to be handled carefully. High training and implementing digital transformation research projects in phases are key to success. Cybersecurity is also a big concern that needs to be handled with care with cybersecurity investment to mitigate the risk. Investing in robust cybersecurity frameworks and employee awareness programs is essential to safeguard organizational data and maintain consumer trust.

Opportunity Capabilities. Digital transformation presents numerous opportunities for revenue growth and sustainability. The integration of the Internet of Things (IoT) enhances supply chain visibility, resource efficiency, and environmental performance. Retailers that embrace these technologies are better positioned to drive innovation, achieve long-term sustainability goals, and secure a competitive advantage in the evolving digital economy.

9.0 Limitations of the findings

Generalization Concerns. The findings and results may not reflect all retail context across the industry because the retail industry consists of diverse players ranging from small independent shops to large multinational chains. Each operates under different business models, technology adoption levels, and demographic settings. Therefore, conclusions drawn from one context—such as large retailers in Cape Town—may not accurately represent smaller or less digitally mature firms operating in other regions.

Interpretation bias. The possibility of bias from the interpretations which may be influenced by original authors leading to skew conclusions of the research. Therefore, the conclusions drawn in this research could reflect the perspectives of prior researchers rather than the absolute state of the retail environment.

Overreliance on existing literature. Findings from existing literature may be influenced by old existing theories and frameworks rather than current and future developments, and this can lead to outdated conclusions since technology is evolving at a fast pace. This reliance on outdated sources may limit the applicability of the findings to current and future retail developments.

Data integration. Combining data from different secondary sources is challenging because different authors use different methodologies, definitions, and analytics, and it can lead to inconsistency in findings reducing its reliability. Therefore, the findings might not provide a fully unified understanding of digital transformation in the retail sector.

10.0 Challenges faced when Implementing Digital Transformation Initiatives

System integration. Many retailers are still using old systems which are not compatible with new digital technologies, making it difficult to integrate (Bjerke-Busch and Aspelund, 2021). This

lack of compatibility between traditional systems and new technologies complicates integration, which leads to inefficiencies and increased implementation costs.

Data management. Retailers find it difficult to manage vast amounts of data and ensuring its security is always a concern (Mentsiev et al, 2023). Retailers must balance the need for real-time data analytics with the responsibility to protect consumer privacy and comply with data protection regulations.

Employee resistance. It is difficult for employees to accept changes of environment from one system to another, and others tend to resist changes while others find it difficult to adapt (Furxhi, 2021). Employees often feel threatened by automation systems which makes them hesitant to learn new systems, and this slows down implementation and reduces the overall effectiveness of transformation initiatives.

Skill gap. Lack of skill to work with modern technologies from both employee and customers can affect digital transformation adoption (Feijao, 2021). Employees may lack the technical expertise needed to manage advanced technologies, while customers may struggle to engage with new digital channels.

Cost constraints. High upfront costs and maintenance expenses for digital transformation initiatives and keeping up with fast pace of technology advancement can be difficult (Hassan et al, 2024). Budget limitations, especially among small and medium enterprises (SMEs), make it difficult to sustain long-term digital transformation strategies.

11.0 Barriers of digital transformation facing retail industry

Limited access. Limited access to high-speed internet and reliable electricity hampers the adoption of digital technologies such online digital channels (Ebrahim and Van Der Berg, 2024). The successful adoption of online digital platforms, e-commerce systems, and cloud-based services depends on stable digital infrastructure. Inconsistent power supply and limited internet coverage restrict both consumers and businesses from fully utilizing digital tools for transactions, communication, and operations.

Digital literacy. Low levels of digital literacy among consumers and employees slow down the adoption of digital solutions (Adel, 2024). Many workers lack the technical knowledge required

to operate new systems such as AI-driven tools, CRM software, and e-commerce platforms, leading to the under-use of technology investments. On the consumer side, limited familiarity with online platforms discourages engagement with digital channels and limits the potential of omnichannel retail strategies.

Regulatory compliance. Many organizations have challenges navigating complex regulating environments which include data protection laws and consumer protection regulation (Matsepe and Van Der Lingen, 2022). Organizations must comply with data protection laws, cybersecurity regulations, and consumer protection policies that govern online transactions and the use of personal data. Failure to adhere to these regulations can result in significant financial penalties and damage to reputation. The evolving nature of digital laws with limited legal and technical expertise among retailers makes compliance a difficult and costly process.

Economic challenges. Income inequality and high unemployment rates hamper consumer spending, and this affects digital transformation adoption (Ebrahim and Van Der Berg, 2024). When consumer purchasing power is low, businesses face reduced incentives to invest in advanced digital systems aimed at enhancing customer experience and engagement. Additionally, the financial constraints experienced by smaller retailers make it difficult to afford technology upgrades, staff training, and long-term maintenance of digital platforms.

REFERENCES

Vial, G. (2019). Understanding digital transformation: A review and a research agenda. *The Journal of Strategic Information Systems*, 28(2), 118–144.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsis.2019.01.003>

Tang, D. (2021). WHAT IS DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION?. *EDPACS*. 64. 9-13. 10.1080/07366981.2020.1847813.

Brynjolfsson, E., & Hitt, L. M. (n.d.). Beyond computation: Information technology, Organizational Transformation and Business Performance. *Journal of Economic Perspectives*. <https://www.aeaweb.org/articles?id=10.1257%2Fjep.14.4.23>

Trenz, M., Veit, D. J., & Tan, C.-W. (2020). Disentangling the impact of Omnichannel Integration on consumer behavior in integrated sales channels. *MIS Quarterly*, 44(3), 1207–1258. <https://doi.org/10.25300/misq/2020/14121>

Sunikka A & Bragge J. (2012). Pantano, E., & Viassone, M. (2015a). Engaging consumers on new integrated multichannel retail settings: Challenges for retailers. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 25, 106–114. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jretconser.2015.04.003>

Shi, S., Wang, Y., Chen, X., & Zhang, Q. (2020). Conceptualization of omnichannel customer experience and its impact on shopping intention: A mixed-method approach. *International Journal of Information Management*. 50. 325-336. 10.1016/j.ijinfomgt.2019.09.001

Faraj, S., & Leonardi, P. M. (2022). Strategic organization in the digital age: Rethinking the concept of Technology. *Strategic Organization*, 20(4), 771–785. <https://doi.org/10.1177/14761270221130253>

Pantano, E., & Viassone, M. (2015a). Engaging consumers on new integrated multichannel retail settings: Challenges for retailers. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 25, 106–114. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jretconser.2015.04.003>

Rathore, B. (2019). Exploring the Impact of Digital Transformation on Marketing Management Strategies. *Eduzone : international peer reviewed/refereed academic multidisciplinary journal*. 8. 2319-5045. 10.56614/eiprmj.v8i2y19.366.

Zhang, X., Park, Y., Park, J., & Zhang, H. (2024). Demonstrating the influencing factors and outcomes of customer experience in Omnichannel retail. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 77, 103622. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jretconser.2023.103622>

Cao, L., & Li, L. (2018). Determinants of retailers' cross-channel integration: An innovation diffusion perspective on omni-channel retailing. *Journal of Interactive Marketing*, 44(1), 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.intmar.2018.04.003>

Shukla, M., & Gupta, R. (2022a). Effect of social media personalization on brand strength. *International Journal of Online Marketing*, 12(1), 1–22. <https://doi.org/10.4018/ijom.299401>

Vuong, B. N., Voak, A., Hossain, S. F., Phuoc, N. T., & Dang, L. H. (2024a). The impact of corporate social responsibility on customer loyalty through Brand Trust and Brand Reputation: Evidence from low-cost airlines. *Transportation Research Procedia*, 80, 111–118. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trpro.2024.09.015>

Riegger, A.-S., Klein, J. F., Merfeld, K., & Henkel, S. (2021). Technology-enabled personalization in retail stores: Understanding Drivers and barriers. *Journal of Business Research*, 123, 140–155. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2020.09.039>

Brown, W., Wilson, G., & Johnson, O. (2024). Exploring the Adoption of Digital Payment Systems in Retail. <https://doi.org/10.20944/preprints202407.2424.v1>

Krishnan, C., Gupta, A., Gupta, A., & Singh, G. (2022). Impact of artificial intelligence-based chatbots on customer engagement and business growth. *Studies in Big Data*, 195–210. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-10869-3_11

Gupta, V., Gupta, L., & Dhir, S. (2020). Customer competency for improving firm decision-making performance in e-commerce. *Foresight*, 22(2), 205–222. <https://doi.org/10.1108/fs-06-2019-0053>

Cotarelo, M., Calderón, H., & Fayos, T. (2021). A further approach in omnichannel LSQ, Satisfaction and Customer Loyalty. *International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management*, 49(8), 1133–1153. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ijrdm-01-2020-0013>

Hsu, C.-L., Chang, C.-Y., & Yansritakul, C. (2017). Exploring purchase intention of green skincare products using the theory of planned behavior: Testing the moderating effects of country of origin and price sensitivity. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 34, 145–152. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jretconser.2016.10.006>

Niedrich, R. W., Weathers, D., Hill, R. C., & Bell, D. R. (2009). Specifying price judgments with range– frequency theory in models of Brand choice. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 46(5), 693–702. <https://doi.org/10.1509/jmkr.46.5.693>

Anthony, J. (2024, February 28). How businesses can leverage health conscious consumer behavior. *Leger*. <https://leger360.com/en/4-things-brands-need-to-know-to-effectively-engage-with-health-conscious-consumers/>

Jain, G., Paul, J., & Shrivastava, A. (2021). Hyper-personalization, co-creation, digital clienteling and transformation. *Journal of Business Research*, 124, 12–23.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2020.11.034>

Largan, C., & Morris, T. (2019). *Qualitative Secondary Research: A step-by-step guide*. SAGE.

Miles, B., & Huberman M. *Qualitative Data Analysis: An expanded sourcebook*. (1994). *Journal of Environmental Psychology*, 14(4), 336–337. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0272-4944\(05\)80231-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0272-4944(05)80231-2)

Mentsiev, A., Aygumov, T., & Amirova, E. (2023). DATA-DRIVEN DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION: CHALLENGES AND STRATEGIES FOR EFFECTIVE BIG DATA MANAGEMENT. 18. 526-531. 10.24412/1932-2321-2023-575-526-531.

Bjerke-Busch, L., & Aspelund, A. (2021). Identifying Barriers for Digital Transformation in the Public Sector. 10.1007/978-3-030-69380-0_15.

Furxhi, G. (2021). Employee's Resistance and Organizational Change Factors. *European Journal of Business and Management Research*. 6. 30-32. 10.24018/ejbmr.2021.6.2.759.

Feijao, C. (2021). The Global Digital Skills Gap: Current Trends and Future Directions. <https://doi.org/10.7249/rra1533-1>

Hassan, A. M., Negash, Y. T., & Hanum, F. (2024). An assessment of barriers to digital transformation in circular construction: An application of stakeholder theory. *Ain Shams Engineering Journal*, 15(7), 102787. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asej.2024.102787>

Ebrahim, A., & Van Den Berg, C. (2024). The barriers to technology adoption among businesses in the informal economy in Cape Town. *South African Journal of Information Management*. 26. 10.4102/sajim.v26i1.1872

Adel, N. (2024). The Impact of Digital Literacy and Technology Adoption on Financial Inclusion: Evidence from Emerging Economies in Africa, Asia, and Latin America. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4938481>

Matsepe, N. T., & Van der Lingen, E. (2022). Determinants of emerging technologies adoption in the South African Financial Sector. *South African Journal of Business Management*, 53(1). <https://doi.org/10.4102/sajbm.v53i1.2493>